

Introduction

We are inviting participants associated with an organisation or business that has interests in the space sector to answer our online survey. The survey is designed to help us understand the ways businesses and organisations engage in sustainability practices as well as ask for participants' insight for the future of the industry in Aotearoa New Zealand.

We encourage responses from participants who are familiar with sustainability in their business/organisation as well as those who may not have considered it previously. The survey includes Likert scale questions and optional open-ended questions and should take approximately 10 minutes to complete. A summary of the findings will be available to interested participants as indicated on the final page of this survey.

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you may leave the online survey at any point prior to submission without any responses being recorded. Once you have submitted your responses, you will no longer be given the opportunity to alter them, and we will not be able to remove them from the dataset as they are anonymous. **Submission of your survey responses will be taken as consent of participation in the research.**

Approved by the University of Auckland Human Participants Ethics Committee on 06/05/2022 for three years. Reference Number UAHPEC24002.

Firstly, we'd like to know a little bit about your business and the work you do in the space sector.

What industry is your business in?

What position do you currently hold?

In what country is your business headquartered?

In what country do most of your business' operations take place?

Approximately how many people work at your business?

- 1-5
- 6-20
- 21-50
- 51-100
- 100+

At the University of Auckland, we are interested in improving our understanding of sustainability in the space sector of Aotearoa and exploring how our businesses and communities feel about sustainability. We value your opinions on this issue and have a few

questions so we can get your perspective. There are no right or wrong answers; we are interested in what you have to say.

Based on your understanding of sustainability, please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Sustainability is an important goal for the space sector of Aotearoa	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Sustainable business practices are common in the space sector	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
My business takes sustainability into account in what we do	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I have a good understanding of what sustainability in the space sector means	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

In your opinion, what are the three most important issues facing the space sector in Aotearoa right now (e.g., international competitiveness, need for technological innovation, environmental regulations)?

Issue 1

Issue 2

Issue 3

When you think about '**sustainability in the space sector**', what comes to mind? Please select as many or as few of the issues below that you associate with sustainability or lack of sustainability.

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| ☐ climate change | ☐ orbital space debris | ☐ the environmental impact of space launch facilities being built on earth |
| ☐ emissions from launches | ☐ falling space debris | ☐ the environmental impact of structures being built on other astronomical bodies |
| ☐ noise and vibration from launches | ☐ the visual impact of structures introduced into Earth's orbit | ☐ exploitation of other astronomical bodies for resources |
| ☐ ozone depletion | ☐ preserving materials from early space missions | ☐ altering the atmosphere/climates of other astronomical bodies |
| ☐ ocean pollution | ☐ managing limited natural resources | ☐ disrupting mineral or water resources on other astronomical bodies |
| ☐ jettisoned launch stages | ☐ managing waste from human expansion into space | ☐ changing pristine landscapes on other astronomical bodies |

Other:

Do you consider 'sustainability in the space sector' to be mostly about sustainability on Earth or about sustainability in space and on other astronomical bodies (e.g., planets, asteroids)? Please click on the slider even if it is already where you want it, otherwise the survey won't record your answer.

In your opinion, what are the two top priorities for space in the next 20 years?

Priority 1

Priority 2

We're interested in knowing some of the reasons why sustainability might **not** be a goal for your business or may be difficult for your business to achieve. Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
My business doesn't have the resources or funding needed to improve sustainability	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Investing in sustainability won't give us a good return on our investment	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
I don't know how to improve sustainability in my business	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It's not clear how issues like climate change are relevant to my business	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
My business has too many other goals and projects right now to focus on sustainability	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Focusing on sustainability could reduce the competitiveness of my business	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Compared to other industries, the space sector barely has an impact on the environment	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The space sector is already doing a great job in terms of sustainability	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
There is little value in focusing on sustainability	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Other:

These questions ask about support that might be needed by the space sector to move towards sustainability. Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
The government should be leaders in sustainability and the environment, with the space sector providing support	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
The space sector should be leaders in sustainability and the environment, with the government providing support	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It is important that the government help fund local businesses to encourage sustainability	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It would be good to have some general guidance and information for businesses on what steps they can take towards sustainability	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
It would be good to have regulations and standards about sustainability in the space sector	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Are there any particular people or organisations that you would prefer to get guidance and information on sustainability from?

Are there any key documents that you get guidance and information on sustainability from? (e.g., guidelines, treaties, conventions, handbooks, etc.)

Are there any other forms of support you'd like to see offered to the space sector to improve sustainability (e.g., changes in policy, increased funding)?

If sustainable business practices are able to provide any of the following opportunities for your business, which ones would you be interested in? Please use the slider to indicate how much the following opportunities would be of interest to your business. Please click on the slider even if it is already where you want it, otherwise the survey won't record your answer.

Other:

A final question to conclude this survey:

Are you interested in receiving a summary of the results from this survey?

If yes, you will be redirected to a separate form to enter your email address. **Your contact details will never be connected with your responses in this survey.**

Yes

No

We welcome your feedback! If you have any other comments you would like to make about sustainability in the space sector or the survey, please make them below.

Please click the forward arrow to finish the survey and submit your answers.

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